

Kinetics and Mechanism of Formation of Dichloromono-(amidinothiourea)platinum(II) from PtCl_4^{2-} and Amidinothiourea in Aqueous Acid Chloride Medium^ψ

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Kinetics of formation of dichloromono(amidinothiourea)platinum(II) from PtCl_4^{2-} and amidinothiourea in acidic aqueous solution have been studied. The protonation constant of the ligand, amidinothiourea (L), and the equilibrium constants for the following reactions have been evaluated :

From the observed dependence of the rate of the reaction on concentrations of the ligand, H^+ and Cl^- ions, a plausible mechanism has been proposed. Activation parameters corresponding to the resolved rate constants have also been evaluated.

Amidinothiourea ($\text{L} = \text{H}_2\text{N}-\overset{\text{S}}{\underset{||}{\text{C}}}-\text{NH}-\overset{\text{NH}}{\underset{||}{\text{C}}}-\text{NH}_2$) is a bidentate ligand having the ability to bind through N,N or N,S binding sites. This forms exceptionally stable complexes with metal ions, including d^8 ions which form square-planar complexes. In case of Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} the ligand is known¹ to form 6-membered chelate ring binding through N and S. Extensive studies on the ligand replacement reactions of Pt^{II} and Pd^{II} have shown²⁻⁵ that the rates of these reactions are generally dependent on the concentration of the incoming ligand and its nature. Several kinetic studies on ligand replacement reactions of Pt^{II} have been reported⁵⁻¹⁴. Results of kinetic studies on the formation of the dichloro-mono(amidinothiourea)-platinum(II) in the reaction of PtCl_4^{2-} with amidinothiourea in aqueous HCl medium in presence of excess Cl^- ion are reported in this communication.

Results and Discussion

Spectral observations indicate that in aqueous hydrochloric acid (ca. 0.05–0.25 mol dm⁻³) in presence of excess chloride (KCl , 0.3–1.0 mol dm⁻³), PtCl_4^{2-} reacts with excess amidinothiourea (L) forming $\text{PtCl}_2(\text{=L})$. The observations indicate that under these conditions the product complex remains in equilibrium with the reactant and hence the extent of reaction depends on the concentration of the ligand (L). At fixed concentrations of H^+ and Cl^- and under pseudo-first order conditions ($[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{Cl}^-]$, $T_L \gg [\text{PtCl}_4^{2-}]$) at a constant ionic strength, the observed value of the pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) is a composite one corresponding to a path which is first-order in ligand concentration with a concurrent ligand-independent path where presumably the reaction

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proceeds via solvolysis, a behaviour typical for ligand replacement reactions of square-planar complexes,

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_L T_L \quad (1)$$

where T_L is the concentration of the added ligand (L) in the solution. Both k_0 and k_L are composite constants as shown below. k_{obs} also varies with $[H^+]$ and $[Cl^-]$ and the results of detailed studies are in conformity with Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Under the experimental conditions, $\log K_H$ values evaluated by pH-metric method are 5.66 ± 0.03 . This means that in the range of acid concentration used in the experiments ($0.08\text{--}0.25 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) virtually all the amidinothiourea exists in the monoprotonated form (LH^+).

Assuming steady state concentration for the in-

termediate species (II), i.e. $\text{PtCl}_3(\text{OH}_2)^-$, we have

$$[II] = \frac{k_1[I]}{k_2[\text{LH}^+] + k_{-1}[\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (2)$$

Therefore,

$$[III] = \frac{k_1 K_a [I]}{k_2[\text{LH}^+] + k_{-1}[\text{Cl}^-][\text{H}^+]} \quad (3)$$

Hence, based on Scheme 1 under pseudo-first order conditions, i.e. $[\text{PtCl}_4^{2-}] \ll [\text{LH}^+], [\text{H}^+], [\text{Cl}^-]$,

$$\begin{aligned}
 k_{\text{obs}} = & k_3 [\text{LH}^+] + k_{-3} [\text{Cl}^-] + \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{LH}^+]}{k_2[\text{LH}^+] + k_{-1}[\text{Cl}^-]} \\
 & + \frac{k_1 k'_2 K_a [\text{LH}^+]}{k_2[\text{LH}^+] + k_{-1}[\text{Cl}^-][\text{H}^+]} \quad (4)
 \end{aligned}$$

If $k_2[\text{LH}^+] \gg k_{-1} [\text{Cl}^-]$ as is likely, then

$$k_{\text{obs}} \approx k_3 [\text{LH}^+] + \left\{ k_{-3}[\text{Cl}^-] + k_1 + \frac{k_1 k'_2 K_a}{k_2[\text{H}^+]} \right\} \quad (5)$$

At fixed $[\text{H}^+]$ and $[\text{Cl}^-]$ equation (5) corresponds to equation (1) with

$$k_L = k_3 \text{ and } k_0 = k_{-3}[\text{Cl}^-] + k_1 + \frac{k_1 k'_2 K_a}{k_2[\text{H}^+]}$$

When $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ are held constant, plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{LH}^+]$ is linear (Figs. 1(A) and 1(B)) with slope, $S_1 = k_3$, and intercept,

$$I_1 = k_{-3} [\text{Cl}^-] + k_1 + \frac{k_1 k'_2 K_a}{k_2[\text{H}^+]}$$

Plot of I_1 vs $[\text{Cl}^-]$ at fixed $[\text{H}^+]$ is also linear (Fig. 2) with slope, $S_2 = k_{-3}$ and intercept,

$$I_2 = k_1 + \frac{k_1 k'_2 K_a}{k_2[\text{H}^+]}$$

Again, plot of I_2 vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ is linear (Fig 3) with slope, $S_4 = \frac{k_1 k'_2 K_a}{k_2}$ and intercept, $I_4 = k_1$.

Further, plot of I_1 vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$ is linear at fixed $[\text{Cl}^-]$ (Fig. 4) with slope, $S_3 = k_1 k'_2 K_a / k_2[\text{H}^+]$ and intercept, $I_3 = k_1 + k_{-3} [\text{Cl}^-]$. From the linear plot of I_3 vs $[\text{Cl}^-]$ (Fig. 5) the k_1 value is also obtained as intercept (I_5) and k_{-3} value from slope (S_5).

Fig. 1. Formation of dichloro-mono(amidinothiourea)platinum(II) from PtCl_4^{2-} and amidinothiourea (L) in aqueous acid-chloride media (temp. = 35° : Evaluation of k_3 , see text).

(A) Effect of variation of ligand concentration $[\text{LH}^+]$ on rate constant at different $[\text{H}^+]$: $[\text{PtCl}_4^{2-}] = 0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{LH}^+] = 0.04\text{--}0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}^+] = 0.08, 0.10, 0.125 \text{ and } 0.20 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for A-D, E-H, I-L and M-P respectively; $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for A, E, I and M, 0.5 mol dm^{-3} for B, F, J and N, 0.75 mol dm^{-3} for C, G, K and O and 1.0 mol dm^{-3} for D, H, L and P; $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (HCl + KCl + KNO_3).

(B) Effect of variation of ligand concentration $[\text{LH}^+]$ on rate constant at different $[\text{H}^+]$ at different $[\text{Cl}^-]$: $[\text{PtCl}_4^{2-}] = 0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{LH}^+] = 0.04\text{--}0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{H}^+] = 0.08 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for A, E, I and M, 0.10 mol dm^{-3} for B, F, J and N, $0.125 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for C, G, K and O, 0.20 mol dm^{-3} for D, H, L and P, 0.25 mol dm^{-3} for Q; $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.3, 0.5, 0.75 \text{ and } 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ for A-D, E-H, I-L and M-Q respectively; $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (HCl + KCl + KNO_3).

By the graphical evaluations outlined above it was thus possible to obtain the values of k_3 and two sets of values of each of the constants k_{-3} ,

k_1 and $k_1 k'_2 K_a / k_2$; both sets of values in each case were in good agreement. All these values were evaluated at three different temperatures and these

Fig. 2. Evaluation of k_3 (see text) : plots of I_1 vs $[Cl^-]$ at different $[H^+]$ (temp. = 35°) : $[H^+]$, 0.08, 0.10, 0.125 and 0.20 mol dm^{-3} for A, B, C and D respectively.

Fig. 4. Evaluation of $k_1k_2'K_a/k_2$: plots of I_1 vs $1/[H^+]$ at different $[Cl^-]$ (temp. = 35°) : $[Cl^-]$, 0.3, 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0 mol dm^{-3} for A, B, C and D respectively.

Fig. 3. Evaluation of k_1 and $k_1k_2'K_a/k_2$: plots of I_2 vs $1/[H^+]$

Fig. 5. Evaluation of k_3 and k_1 : plots of I_3 vs $[Cl^-]$. Eyring equation¹⁵, and these values are also given in Table 1. At 35° ($I = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3}) the average value of k_1 is 2.19×10^{-4} s^{-1} which is in fair agreement with the calculated k_1 value of 1.76×10^{-4} s^{-1} based on the ΔH^\ddagger (87.86 kJ mol^{-1}) and ΔS^\ddagger (-33.47 J K^{-1} mol^{-1}) values reported by Martin *et al.*¹⁶ at an ionic strength of 0.30 mol dm^{-3} . The ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger values obtained using the

are given in Table 1. From the $k_1k_2'K_a/k_2$ values thus obtained and a knowledge of K_a value evaluated experimentally by equilibrium method (loc. cit.) and of k_1 obtained from kinetic data as above, two sets of values of k_2'/k_2 were also obtained which were in good agreement. From the values of k_3 and the average values of k_3 and k_1 at three different temperatures, the corresponding activation parameters ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were evaluated using

TABLE 1—VALUES OF THE EVALUATED KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE FORMATION OF DICHLOROMONO(AMIDINOTHIUREA)-PLATINUM(II) FROM PtCl_4^{2-} IN AQUEOUS HCl-KCl MEDIUM

$[\text{PtCl}_4^{2-}] = 0.002 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{LH}^+] = 0.04\text{--}0.10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.05\text{--}0.25 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Cl}^-] = 0.3\text{--}1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$,
 $l = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ [HCl + KCl + KNO₃ (where necessary)]

Temp. °C	k_3 dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^2 k_3$, dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$10^4 k_1$,	$10^4 \left(\frac{k_1 k_2' K_a}{k_2} \right)$	$10^{-7} \left(\frac{k_2'}{k_2} \right)$
35	0.14 ^a	1.04 ^b	2.27 ^b	7.73 ^b	5.1
		1.02 ^c	2.10 ^c	8.13 ^c	5.8
		1.03(av.)	2.19(av.)	7.93(av.)	5.45(av.)
40	0.29 ^a	1.76 ^b	4.06 ^b	9.29 ^b	7.2
		1.69 ^c	3.86 ^c	10.00 ^c	8.1
		1.73(av.)	3.96(av.)	9.65(av.)	7.65(av.)
45	0.55 ^a	2.61 ^b	6.71 ^b	9.57 ^b	9.1
		2.71 ^c	6.47 ^c	9.10 ^c	9.0
		2.66(av.)	6.59(av.)	9.34(av.)	9.05(av.)
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)		110.6 ± 1.1	75.2 ± 2.2	87.8 ± 1.9	
ΔS^\ddagger (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)		96.2 ± 3.4	-40.7 ± 7.1	-31.9 ± 6.1	

^a k_3 values obtained from the slopes of the linear plot of k_{obs} vs $[\text{LH}^+]$ at fixed $[\text{Cl}^-]$. ^bFrom ligand variation at different $[\text{Cl}^-]$ at fixed $[\text{H}^+]$ (0.08, 0.10, 0.125 and 0.20 mol dm⁻³) (see text). ^cFrom ligand variation at different $[\text{H}^+]$ at fixed $[\text{Cl}^-]$ (0.3, 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0 mol dm⁻³) (see text).

average values of k_1 of the present investigation are also in fair agreement with the corresponding literature values¹⁶.

For the associative reactions of PtCl_4^{2-} with the ligands diethyl sulphide (Et_2S)^{11a} and 1,3-diaminopropane (dmp)^{11b}, the reported k_L values are 0.12 and $2.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively, at 25°. Again, for the corresponding reactions of PtCl_4^{2-} with ammonia^{12a} and thiourea^{12b} the k_L values are 4.5×10^{-3} and $2.0 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively, at 55°. Hence, the reaction of PtCl_4^{2-} with a ligand binding through a S donor proceeds significantly faster than that of one proceeding by bond formation through N donor of a ligand. Hence, the observed magnitude of k_3 value for the reaction of PtCl_4^{2-} with amidinothiourea suggests that in the rate-determining step the unidentate binding of the ligand involves formation of Pt-S bond with amidinothiourea, followed by a fast ring closure involving second bond formation through the N donor site leading to the product chelate complex $\text{PtCl}_2(\text{=L})$.

The observed ratio of k_2'/k_2 is $\sim 10^7$ indicating that the hydroxo complex $\text{PtCl}_3(\text{OH})^{2-}$ is very much more reactive than the corresponding aquo complex $\text{PtCl}_3(\text{OH}_2)^-$. Generally¹⁴ the hydroxo complex is much more reactive than the corresponding aquo complex in almost all the known cases, but the difference is generally not so large as observed in the present system. However, for the reaction of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{OH})^{3-}$ with SCN^- , the reported rate constant at 25° is $1.3 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (k_f^{OH})¹⁷ while for the corresponding reaction of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5(\text{OH}_2)^{2-}$ the value is $1.96 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($k_f^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$)¹⁷. Thus, the ratio ($k_f^{\text{OH}}/k_f^{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$) in this case is 6.6×10^7 .

Experimental

Amidinothiourea was prepared in pure state by known method¹⁸ and its purity was checked by chemical analysis and melting point (170°). Stock solution of K_2PtCl_4 was prepared by dissolving pure potassium tetrachloroplatinate(II) (Arora Matthey, Calcutta) in aqueous KCl and was standardised by usual gravimetric method¹⁹. This stock solution

Fig 6 Plots of $\bar{n}_H / (1 - \bar{n}_H)$ vs $[H^+]$ for evaluation of K_H for amidinothiourea (L) · (A) 35°, (B) 40°, (c) 45°.

was kept in a Jena glass bottle and stored in the dark protected from light. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade. Double-distilled water was used to prepare the solutions, the second distillation being carried out from alkaline permanganate solution.

A Carl-Zeiss VSU-2P spectrophotometer (Jena, Germany) was used for absorbance measurements. As the rate of formation of $PtCl_2(=L)$ from $PtCl_4^{2-}$ is moderately fast, the kinetic experiments were performed using a Canterbury model stopped-flow spectrophotometer (SF-3A, Hi-Tech, England) coupled with a microprocessor supplied by the manufacturer. The reacting solutions and the observation cell were kept thermostated at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). Measurements of pH were made with a Systronics (India) 335 digital pH meter.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF LOG K_H AND THE THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS (ΔH , ΔS) CORRESPONDING TO K_H (SEE TEXT)

$I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ (KCl)}$		
Temp		log K_H
°C		
35		5.69 ± 0.02
40		5.66 ± 0.02
45		5.63 ± 0.02
ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)		-10.6 ± 0.2
ΔS (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)		75.3 ± 0.7

Determination of the protonation constant of amid-

inothiourea (L) in aqueous KCl medium : The K_H value corresponding to the following reaction [equation (6)] was evaluated experimentally by Bjerrum's method²⁰ with appropriate modifications^{21,22} under conditions similar to those used for kinetic measurements,

The experimental procedure involved measurements of the pH of the solutions containing known amount of the amidinothiourea ($0.005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in presence of different known amounts (5×10^{-4} to $4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) of a mineral acid (HCl) at a constant ionic strength (1.0 mol dm^{-3} , adjusted with KCl) and a fixed temperature. The actual $[H^+]$ of the solutions were obtained from measured pH and referring to a pH vs $[H^+]$ calibration curve of the electrode system used. The average number of protons $[H^+]$ bound per molecule of the ligand (\bar{n}_H) were calculated following the procedure of Irving and Rossotti²². The plot of $\bar{n}_H / (1 - \bar{n}_H)$ vs $[H^+]$ was a straight line passing through origin whose slope gave the value of K_H (Fig. 6). From the values of K_H at three different temperatures the corresponding thermodynamic parameters (ΔH and ΔS) were evaluated. The results are given in Table 2.

Determination of the stepwise equilibrium constants for formation of $PtCl_3(OH)^{2-}$ from $PtCl_4^{2-}$: The following equilibria are of consideration,

Considering the above equilibria in an aqueous solution of $PtCl_4^{2-}$ ($0.0005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in presence of excess Cl^- ($0.3-1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), K_1 and K_a values could be evaluated graphically from the measured values of $[H^+]$ in the solution.

For this purpose, pH measurements were made of aqueous solutions of $PtCl_4^{2-}$ containing different amounts of Cl^- (KCl) after being equilibrated at the desired temperature. The total ionic strength of the medium was maintained at 1.0 mol dm^{-3}

using KNO_3 in addition to KCl where necessary. The actual values of $[\text{H}^+]$ of the solutions were obtained from measured pH values by referring to the pH vs $[\text{H}^+]$ calibration curve of the electrode system used. From the equations (6a) and (6b) it follows,

$$\{T_{\text{Pt}}[\text{H}^+]\}/[\text{H}^+]^2 = (T_{\text{Cl}}/K_1K_a) + 1/K_a \quad (7)$$

where T_{Pt} and T_{Cl} are the total concentrations of PtCl_4^{2-} and Cl^- respectively, in the solution. The plot of $\{T_{\text{Pt}}[\text{H}^+]\}/[\text{H}^+]^2$ vs T_{Cl} was linear (Fig. 7) with a slope equal to $1/K_1K_a$ and an intercept equal to $1/K_a$. From the least-squares values of the slope and intercept, K_1 and K_a were evaluated. From the values of K_1 and K_a at three different temperatures, the corresponding thermodynamic parameters (ΔH and ΔS) were evaluated. The results are given in Table 3.

Fig 7 Plots of $\{T_{\text{Pt}}[\text{H}^+]\}/[\text{H}^+]^2$ vs T_{Cl} for PtCl_4^{2-} in acid chloride media for evaluation of K_1 and K_a . $T_{\text{Pt}} = 0.0005 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $T_{\text{Cl}} = 0.3\text{--}0.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-1}$ ($\text{KCl} + \text{KNO}_3$)

The rate of formation of $\text{PtCl}_2(=\text{L})$ has been followed under pseudo-first order conditions at 400 nm, where the difference in absorbance of the reactant and the product is quite appreciable, in aqueous acid media containing excess chloride in presence of excess ligand (L). The ionic strength

of the medium was maintained at 1.0 mol dm^{-3} using KCl and KNO_3 where necessary. The effect of H^+ has been studied at 0.08 to 0.20 (0.25 in one case) mol dm^{-3} HCl at each of the $[\text{Cl}^-]$ of 0.3, 0.5, 0.75 and 1.0 mol dm^{-3} . The effect of chloride ion has been studied at 0.3 to 1.0 mol dm^{-3} $[\text{Cl}^-]$ at each of the $[\text{H}^+]$ of 0.08, 0.10, 0.125 and 0.20 mol dm^{-3} . The microprocessor analysed the stopped flow experimental data to furnish the pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}). Average of at least three k_{obs} values for each set of experiment was used for evaluation of the component rate constants.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF STEPWISE EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS (K_1 AND K_a) IN THE HYDROLYSIS OF PtCl_4^{2-} TO $\text{PtCl}_3(\text{OH})^2$ AND THE CORRESPONDING THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS (ΔH , ΔS)

$I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($\text{KCl} + \text{KNO}_3$)		
Temp °C	$10^2 K_1$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^8 K_a$ mol dm^{-3}
35	0.88 ± 0.01	6.67 ± 0.03
45	2.96 ± 0.03	1.61 ± 0.01
50	5.76 ± 0.03	0.76 ± 0.01
ΔH (kJ mol ⁻¹)	103.4 ± 2.3	-119.7 ± 1.9
ΔS (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	295.9 ± 7.3	-526.7 ± 6.0

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